

A framework for effective STEAM education: Pedagogy for responding to wicked problems

K. Chappell^{a,b,*}, L. Hetherington^a, S. Juillard^c, C Aguirre^c, E. Duca^d

^a University of Exeter, School of Education, St Lukes Campus, 79 Heavitree Road, Exeter, EX2 4TH, UK

^b Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Inndalsveien 28, 5063 Bergen, Norway

^c Groupe TRACES, Paris, Siège social, 23 rue des Balkans, 75020 Paris, France

^d University of Malta, Room 300, Dar Guzeppi Zahra, Msida, Malta

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

STEAM education
Transdisciplinarity
Educational frameworks
Arts
STEM

ABSTRACT

This conceptual paper articulates a new strategic framework for STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Maths) education in Europe to respond to the challenges facing educators, researchers, students and policy makers. It draws on conceptualisations developed within the EU-funded Road-STEAMer project which is creating a STEAM education roadmap for policymakers at the secondary/ tertiary intersection, particularly in projects that feature open science/schooling and/or responses to ‘grand challenges’. Grounded in the complexity of the current STEAM education landscape, the paper articulates the characteristics of effective STEAM education developed through the Road-STEAMer project, in order to demonstrate how the benefits of STEAM can be catalysed. The paper explains the Road-STEAMer characteristics (equity, disciplinary inter-relationship, collaboration, real-world connections, thinking-making-doing, creativity and inclusion/ empowerment/ personalisation) which were developed from a focused literature review and then considers them in relation to two case studies addressing the post sustainability agenda: Ocean Connections and SciCultureD. Both projects are critically discussed using the Road-STEAMer characteristics to demonstrate the use of modern educational tools in STEAM, alongside how STEAM can contribute to empowering the next generation. The paper concludes by drawing together insights into the significance of the Road-STEAMer characteristics as a strategic framing for catalysing the benefits of STEAM, emphasising the importance of collaboration between researchers and practitioners to achieve this.

1. Introduction

This conceptual paper explains and exemplifies a new strategic framework for STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics) education in Europe to contribute to responding to a number of the current challenges facing educators, researchers, students and policy makers, which have been identified as necessitating investigation by this special issue (Alvarez, Al-Noori, Doval-Ruiz, in preparation). Whilst there are multiple articulations of these challenges, this paper is guided by those identified in 2021, by the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70 funding scheme as: a lack of knowledge regarding European Union (EU) STEAM policy deficiencies and understanding of needs particularly in relation to issues of cultural dynamics; little knowledge around STEAM at the intersection of secondary and tertiary

levels of education, and between education and open science; and sparse awareness for students and citizens about relevant STEAM activities within policy areas such as the European Green Deal, Digitisation and Health.

These challenges can also be found reflected in the peer-reviewed literature. Colucci-Gray, Burnard, Cooke, Davies, Gray, and Trowsdale (2017) remind us that the STEAM acronym exists with a variety of definitions and manifestations in practice, which are not coherently framed. Perignat and Katz-Buonincontro (2019) again emphasise this same point and articulate the variance as to the five disciplines’ integration which become difficult to capture into meaningful policy. This framework and article aim to respond directly to seminal STEAM reviews such as this to contribute alongside those authors to addressing these issues. Regarding cultural dynamics, these can include an array of

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: k.a.chappell@exeter.ac.uk (K. Chappell), l.hetherington@exeter.ac.uk (L. Hetherington), sophie.juillard@groupe-traces.fr (S. Juillard), claudia.aguirre@groupe-traces.fr (C. Aguirre), edward.duca@um.edu.mt (E. Duca).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2025.100474>

Received 13 June 2024; Received in revised form 24 April 2025; Accepted 25 April 2025

Available online 12 May 2025

2666-3740/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

factors such as race, gender, ethnicity, age and heritage and how they manifest intersectionally in terms of power relations between identities and meaning-making (Salehjee & Watts, 2023). Researchers such as Goldschmidt and Bogner (2016) and Perales and Aróstegui (2021) articulate elements of the challenging but potentially beneficial cultural dynamics of STEAM practice but argue that more needs to be done regarding gender especially. Our own work (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a) demonstrates that there are almost no studies examining the secondary tertiary intersection, an area in need of attention therefore, given the significance of this part of young people's progression routes in establishing them as career ready for STEAM/STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths). However, there are a small number of research studies focused on STEAM education and open science (Koul et al., 2021; Research is Your Elevation, 2024), with increasing but still sparse studies of how STEAM education can contribute to sustainability agendas (e.g. Rudd, 2021; Choi et al., 2021; Won et al., 2021). There is therefore a clear gap in the field in both policy and research terms regarding the interrogation of this set of challenges and the provision of a strategic framework which can contribute to addressing them.

The strategic framework that we offer, together with examples from practice to which it is applied have been generated within the Road-STEAMer Horizon-funded project. This was one of three European-wide projects charged with executing the necessary intellectual and policy work over a three-year period to address the above-identified challenges. The project is developing a STEAM policy map that will provide guidance to the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation on how to best utilise STEAM education. This project and the funding stream to which it responds articulate STEAM as focused on the incorporation of 'A' as artistic and applied arts approaches including performing, sound, visual and digital arts, as opposed to STEAM that articulates 'A' as, for example, art in the singular or architecture. The framework therefore reflects this positioning and hopes to extend discussions on these grounds within the breadth of STEAM possibilities. In order for this plan to be grounded in the most up to date knowledge it has been pre-empted by the rigorous literature review and ensuing strategic framework of STEAM characteristics offered here. This will not only serve the wider EU policy imperative but, as per the focus of this paper, simultaneously offer new and significant knowledge to the research community as to how EU STEAM practice can be conceptually framed given the current academic knowledge-base. This is in order to achieve the aims of catalysing the benefits of STEAM defined in this way, and building on previous seminal work in the field to tackle wicked problems. Whilst this paper responds to the challenges regarding a lack of knowledge of STEAM's cultural dynamics, its intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science, this paper is bounded academically in that it does not extend into the possible policy application of this framework. That work is currently ongoing and due for synthesis and publication in 2025 to indicate European policy needs. In the next section, the paper therefore takes time to explain the literature reviewing protocols and analysis which generated the framework and characteristics, and to articulate the ensuing seven inter-related STEAM education characteristics with their related literature.

The paper then goes on to explain how together, these STEAM characteristics are intended to provide a framework within which creative solution-seeking in education can be facilitated in relation to broader societal challenges that can benefit from STEAM approaches. Given the variety of possible STEAM practices and the danger of conceptual explanation being diluted through attempts to encompass all options, the case studies in this paper are considered within one area of STEAM practice. This is the climate emergency and agenda around how we might respond, whether through sustainability or post-sustainability, an area also highlighted as in need of study by the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70 funding call. Once the STEAM characteristics have been articulated, the paper grounds the case studies in current arguments for remaking education for post-sustainability (Sterling, 2017).

This post-sustainability position is prioritised as we agree with its authors who state that the sustainability narratives of neo-liberal, growth-oriented approaches to the climate crisis are in fact unachievable and that we need to resist market growth and centralisation and create space for societal and educational degrowth and decentralisation (Sconfienza, 2019). By applying the STEAM characteristics to the two case study projects we demonstrate how this work can be begun. In line with the thematic agenda of this special issue, we conclude by demonstrating how the STEAM characteristics can catalyse the benefits of STEAM by contributing to a post sustainability response to the climate emergency, which entails adapting STEAM practice to changing times to find resilience in education, employing appropriate digital educational tools and empowering the next generation.

Before articulating the literature review and emergent characteristics, we offer insight into our understanding of STEAM education. STEAM has been developing since around 2010 (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a) and whilst for some it means that the arts extend or improve STEM education (Holbrook, Rannikmäe & Soobard, 2020), the STEM and arts inter-relationship is also conceptualised more equally with the two enmeshed (Burnard and Colucci-Gray, 2020), often in order to respond to 'wicked problems' (Kolko, 2012). Thomassen and Stentoft (2020) define wicked problems as issues that can initially appear too complex to address but that through transdisciplinary practice can be tackled. Here, transdisciplinarity is understood as 'an integrated approach to complex problems using the methodology and insights from a range of disciplines with differing perspectives on the problem under consideration' (Benatar, 2000 p.171). Our working understanding of STEAM education which informs this paper therefore allows for a range of inter-relationships between disciplines but with a keen focus on literature and practices which position 'wicked problems' or grand challenges at their heart.

2. A framework for effective STEAM education

The Road-STEAMer framework for STEAM education was generated from a review of existing literature and practice to synthesise and understand the characteristics of effective STEAM practice. This is with the intention of understanding how STEAM practice in this bounded focus area responds to issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science. The ensuing STEAM characteristics offer a framework within which creative solution-seeking in education can potentially be facilitated, in relation to broader societal challenges or wicked problems.

The Road-STEAMer characteristics were developed from a structured literature review (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a) with protocols applied for rigour in line with Rocco et al. (2023). As they discuss, a structured literature review is a type of systematic review which has a logical, planned structure (Massaro et al., 2016), and follows a detailed step-by-step process. Rocco et al. (2023) discuss how structured reviews are carried out to discover themes and patterns; in this case regarding characteristics for STEAM education in a particular educational context. They articulate that they offer details of the research question/s, method (including material selection and data analysis) and outcomes. For this structured literature review the research question was *What are the criteria (or characteristics) for effective STEAM education in this bounded context?* The bounded context is defined as the intersecting connection between secondary and tertiary, the use of art-oriented approaches or those using creativity, located in practices and thinking explicitly referencing real life settings and grand challenges, in the context of projects and activities engaging in open schooling and/or open science. The review method was carried out predominantly by two collaborating researchers supported by a wider team of consortium partners, during the academic year 2022 to 2023.

Main database searches were carried out on Google, Google Scholar and in University library keyword search and Education databases (Education database; Education Research Complete; British Education

Index; Australian Education Index; ERIC) using the terms: STEAM + education, STEAM + education + arts, STEAM + education + creativ; STEAM Education + Undergraduate + School, STEAM Education + Secondary + Tertiary, STEAM Education + Higher Education + School, STEAM Education + real-world, STEAM Education + real-life challenge. CORDIS was also searched for relevant EU projects and their reports. These initial searches generated 38 peer-reviewed articles or theses, 2 reports, 12 EU specific reports, 7 books and 2 websites. Following Paez (2017) grey literature was also included because it allows for all available evidence on a topic to be included, especially in areas such as this, where little is systematically known. This was gathered via all consortium partners being asked to nominate at least three relevant documents or websites. This generated a further 22 articles, 2 books or book chapters, 4 EU reports and 13 websites or web resources nominated from across the 12 consortium partner organisations. All documents and websites were then read against the following inclusion criteria: publications should be no older than 10 years; dominantly English language with the option to include colleagues' home language publications with translated abstract (however none of the latter were forthcoming); inclusion of criteria, definitions, features or principles of STEAM education within the publication. This process generated 23 articles, 3 reports, 4 books or book chapters, 2 websites and 13 EU projects (detailed in Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a). It is worthy of note that these clustered between 2016 and 2022, the last 7 years of the potential 10. This is perhaps due to the specificity of the combined inclusion criteria and these STEAM elements only coming into the research spotlight more recently than 2013.

These publications were then included in a large-scale thematic analysis using the digital tool Mural to share colour-coded characteristics from each document or website, and then to thematically organise these into STEAM Roadmap relevant characteristics, using the principles of constant comparative analysis (Fram, 2013). This culminated in an analysis workshop between the two lead researchers and the supporting consortium partners to facilitate dialogue and to check and hone the presented analysis with knowledgeable peers. This involved participants suggesting changes to the language used to articulate characteristics and discussion of the inter-relation of the characteristics. It should be noted therefore that the framework relies on the sources that were identified

within this systematic literature and the ensuing workshopping processes. This entire process generated the following characteristics (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a): equity as an all-pervasive characteristic; disciplinary inter-relationship particularly acknowledging the arts' contribution; collaboration; involvement of real-world connections; the processes of thinking-making-doing; creativity; and inclusion, empowerment and personalisation. These are articulated below and shown together in Fig. 1. Analysis shows that this framework of characteristics is indebted to other EU-project frameworks such as STEAM INC's (Burns et al., 2021; Carter et al., 2021) Higher Education (HE) STEAM definition and approaches which readers will note contribute variously to the detail of the Road-STEAMer characteristics from the perspective of HE.

2.1. Equity

In STEAM initiatives which featured issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science, a values-based approach to STEAM was an important consideration. Consortium workshop analysis and synthesis indicated that this should be positioned as an all-pervading characteristic. Equity understood as fairness or a sense of justice was important in terms of the nature of the practices and processes taking place, and the outcomes that are aimed for. STEAM can be positioned as a resistance to dominant disciplinary approaches to education (Colucci-Gray et al., 2017), embodying an affirmative ethical stance (Burnard & Colucci-Gray, 2020; Guyotte, 2020). This leads to the design of STEAM activities that deliberately flatten hierarchies between disciplines and recognise the arts as core subjects alongside STEM with equitable access to time and resources (Allina, 2017). It is also argued that enabling students to lead the learning with teachers positioned as facilitators and guides is a common characteristic of this kind of STEAM practice (Allina, 2017), enabling more equitable power relations between different cultural elements. Equity is also highlighted as a possible outcome of STEAM, for example within the production of socially equitable responses to global challenges (Carter et al., 2021). However, this is more aspirational than evidence-based to date.

Fig. 1. Infographic of STEAM characteristics (criteria).

2.2. Disciplinary inter-relationship

Where issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science were considered within STEAM initiatives, attention to disciplinary inter-relationships was palpable. Sometimes, this meant including mixed disciplines or familiarisation with content outside of the discipline (Foundations of STEAM, n.d) or freedom to move between disciplines (Dredd et al., 2021). It also meant the integration of the arts into curriculum and instruction in the STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) disciplines (Katz-Buonincontro, 2018). This characteristic was also about new connections between subjects or skill areas within STEAM (Colucci-Gray et al., 2017; Johnson-Green et al., 2020) or interaction between disciplines (Liu & Wu, 2022). Some argue that this connection-making also relates to students' ability to transfer knowledge between disciplines (Huser et al., 2020). And others see this connection as grounded in classroom environments which are problem-based, with authentic tasks, student choice, technology integration and teacher facilitation (Quigley & Herro, 2019). With varied definitions, some sources refer to STEAM as transdisciplinary (Guyotte, 2020; Liston et al., 2022; Liao, 2016), others as interdisciplinary (Graham, 2021; Won et al., 2021), others as cross-disciplinary (Jesinowska et al., 2020) and others acknowledge STEAM as encompassing inter-, trans- and cross-disciplinarity (Harris & de Bruin, 2018).

Other sources make more dynamic comment on the disciplinary inter-relationship. It is seen as related to values, multi-modality, positivity and unlearning (Burns et al., 2021); as driving change through making, which values experimental and material agency of invention and exchange between arts and science creativities in STEAM (Burnard & Colucci-Gray, 2020); and as developing understanding of disciplinary identities, with personal relevance informing connections between disciplines (Sochaka, Guyott, & Walther, 2016). Where it is articulated, although the arts are seen as sometimes in danger of dilution (Johnson-Green et al., 2020), it is argued they contribute to socio-cultural elements (Hey-Eun, 2021), are a creativity catalyst (Graham, 2021), contribute aesthetic learning (Liu & Wu, 2022), and as featuring the three core arts processes of creating, performing/producing and responding/appreciating (Huser et al., 2020).

2.3. Collaboration

Within STEAM projects focused on issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science, collaboration was often articulated with an emphasis on teacher-student connections, and also external partners, local communities, educational stakeholders and citizens (Burns et al., 2021; CREAM Project, n.d); OSHub Open Science Hub Network, 2022; Liston et al., 2022; ACE (Arts Council England) STEAM toolkit, Colucci-Gray et al., 2017). Different terminologies were used to refer to collaboration including: a 21st century skill set (Bautista, 2021; Graham, 2021; Sarmiento, Morales, Elipane, & Palomar, 2020); Liao, 2016); group working (Burns et al., 2021); teamwork (Shatunova et al., 2019); interaction (Quigley and Herro, 2019). Mechanisms for facilitating collaboration were highlighted including engagement through acceptance (IMuSciCA, 2019); the role of technology (Burns et al., 2021); game-based learning (Liu & Wu, 2022); communication (Liao, 2016); collaborative connections to art forms e.g. music (IMuSciCA, 2019); and between creativity and collaboration (Carter et al., 2021).

Teachers' roles were seen as that of advisor, counsellor and/or guide (Bautista, 2021) and facilitatory rather than directional, forefronting problem solving, authentic tasks, student choice and technology integration (Quigley and Herro, 2019). Teachers were also seen as collaborating with each other, in dialogue, with this seen as fundamental to disciplinary inter-relationship (Harris & de Bruin, 2018). Seeing collaboration and its inherent relationality as part of a wider STEAM culture featuring multi-modality is highlighted by some (Burns et al.,

2021). Within the posthuman paradigm collaboration and relationality are not just articulated between people, but between people and all others (e.g. environment, planet) as a means to respond to Anthropocentric issues (Guyotte, 2020).

2.4. Involving real world connections

Many STEAM practices which consider issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science highlight the importance of the real-world context or connection (e.g. Martinez, 2017; Scuolattiva, n.d.).

This was through exploring cutting-edge issues or 'wicked problems' (e.g. climate change, SciCulture, n.d.) and offering strong connections with such policies as the Strategy for Enhancing Green Skills (European Economic and Social Committee, 2020). Real-world contexts are often linked to problem-solving and inquiry (Chung & Li, 2021; CREAM Project, n.d.) and offer authenticity and purpose to the endeavours (Quigley & Herro, 2019; Chung & Li, 2021). The civic space is suggested as a real-world context that offers connectivity between Higher Education learners and various publics (Burns et al., 2021). Some sources argue that the real-world context offers learners a means to connect their personal meaning-making (within and between disciplines) to the external context (Zhanova, 2017), with others arguing that such connections enable identity development (e.g. enabling girls to identify as change-makers, Ng and Fergusson, 2020). Entrepreneurship appears in STEAM projects (OSHUB, 2022, Center for STEAM Education Research, Science, Communication & Innovation, 2018; Ng and Fergusson, 2020) as a means for connecting to real-world contexts (Won et al., 2021; SciCulture, n.d.). STEAM projects were also identified as developing skills for future careers (Carter et al., 2021; eCraft2Learn, 2019; Sarmiento et al., 2020).

2.5. Thinking-making-doing

This is written with hyphens as 'thinking-making-doing' to emphasise the interactivity of these practices rather than occurring within STEAM in parallel or separately. Different kinds of thinking are often referred to when authors articulate STEAM practices which consider issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science. These include: habits of thinking (Foundations of STEAM website); system thinking (Shatunova et al., 2019); critical thinking (Center for STEAM Education Research, Science Communication and Innovation, 2018; Chung & Li, 2021; Harris & de Bruin, 2018); creative thinking (Harris & de Bruin, 2018); divergent and convergent thinking (Bautista, 2021). However, 'thinking' is not seen as an isolated 'brain-based' activity but is also recognised interacting with wider skill sets to argue for STEAM practices supporting soft skills (CREAM, 2022), 21st century skills (Graham, 2021; ecraft2Learn (2018), problem solving (Center for STEAM Education Research, Science Communication and Innovation, 2018), creative, cognitive and interactive skills (Quigley & Herro, 2019). STEAM practices are also described as functioning in 'hands-on' making and doing practices (Katz-Buonincontro, 2018), in multi-modality 'unlearning' (meaning forgetting current practices and acquiring new perspectives through modes such as the symbolic and graphic) (Burns et al., 2021), uncertainty management (Shatunova et al., 2019) and inquiry-based, real-world learning (Chung & Li, 2021). This reinforces the idea that STEAM is not a sedentary activity.

Making and doing are explicitly articulated interacting with thinking by those involved in the STEAM 'Makers movement' (which emphasises creating as much as consuming) (CREAM Project, n.d.), and those facilitating students as active, constructive and critical learners (Bautista, 2021). Emphasis is also placed on object-based learning; critique, exhibition and critical making derived from arts-based signature pedagogies (Costantino, 2017).

Thinking-making-doing in STEAM was also connected with the

environment, bodies and spatial materiality (Colucci-Gray et al., 2017) to facilitate public visibility; discursive/making; to create physical environmental change (Burns et al., 2021); employ digital technology for co-creation and gamification (CREAM Project, n.d.).

2.6. Creativity

Creativity is identified as a key element of STEAM activity focused on issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science. Creativity is linked to innovation and the production of novelty (Colucci-Gray et al., 2017; Liao, 2016), to playfulness (Martinez, 2017) and to the flow of experience (Dredd et al., 2021). Some sources describe creativity or creative thinking as a skill that is developed in STEAM practices (Harris and de Bruin, 2018; Sughanda et al., 2021; Quigley & Herro, 2019). Elsewhere, creativity is discussed as 'doing', linked to the 'thinking-making-doing' theme. Tools and pedagogies such as digital technologies (Katz-Buonincontro, 2018; Let's STEAM, n.d.) and design thinking (SciCulture, n.d.) are used creatively as part of STEAM practice, with creative activities also seen as a means of connecting disciplines (SciCulture, n.d.) or supporting collaboration (Martinez, 2017). Thus, creativity is seen as both a means of supporting other STEAM characteristics and as an outcome of those practices. It could be argued that the connectivity fostered through creative STEAM practices (Colucci-Gray et al., 2017; Quigley & Herro, 2019) is one means by which STEAM practice can support the links between secondary and tertiary learning and between schools/universities and communities in Open Schooling.

2.7. Inclusion, empowerment and personalisation

The notion of inclusivity is developed across a range of STEAM sources that consider issues of cultural dynamics, the intersection of secondary and tertiary education, and between education and open science. Stemming from the sense that a wider range of interests is included via the Arts, an as-yet-unverified assumption is often made that STEAM is more inclusive than STEM (e.g. eCraft2Learn, 2019; ACE STEAM toolkit, n.d.). It is suggested that acceptance is important in STEAM activity design, ensuring that participants feel able to fully partake regardless of their levels of confidence (Burns et al., 2021). Inclusion is linked to science capital and identity: with STEAM approaches argued as offering a context where young people are more likely to develop their identity, including that STEAM is 'for them' (PHERECLOS (Partnerships for pathways to Higher Education and science engagement in Regional Clusters of Open Schooling), 2020, and that students' active construction of personal meaning through STEAM leads to greater self-efficacy, confidence and motivation towards socio-scientific learning (Bautista, 2021). Huser et al. (2020) argue that STEAM approaches empower young people and promote engagement due to their open-ended nature and via real-world connections. Greater inclusion and empowerment via STEAM may lead to those from under-represented groups such as girls developing identities as change-makers (Won et al., 2021). There is perhaps a shift here from the individualisation noted above in marketised educational models towards the personalisation inherent in more progressive education models within which this kind of STEAM practice positions itself.

3. Applying the framework and characteristics within a defined area of STEAM practice

The above characteristics therefore form a new framework for understanding how STEAM practice can be most effective in this bounded focus area, offering coherence and supporting quality provision, whilst acknowledging and building on previous seminal research in the field. In this context, we are interested in how it can be used to articulate educational creative solution-seeking in response to wicked problems. In order to further understand this we therefore present next, two case

study STEAM projects which respond to the wicked problem of the climate emergency. In so doing, we find resonance with the special issue focus on *Adaptation to Changing Times* and the need to find resilient strategies for STEAM to thrive in rapidly changing dynamic educational environments which are entangled with such wicked problems.

3.1. Focusing on STEAM education for the climate emergency

Internationally, discussions have shifted from a focus on climate change to a focus on the climate emergency (Ripple et al., 2022). This shift has happened because since 1992 there has been a 40% increase in greenhouse gases with current policies estimated to increase global warming by approximately 3°C warming by 2100. Kemp et al. (2022) argue that the consequences could include global societal collapse.

Entwined with these arguments for increased urgency has been a critique of the sustainability agenda. Sterling (2017) argues that when responding to the climate emergency we need to work with a new 'post-sustainability' agenda because the sustainability narratives of neo-liberal, growth-oriented approaches are unachievable. In stating that practice needs to change, Sterling (2017) pre-empts Ripple et al. (2022) arguments for socially just climate adaptations, including tackling ecological overshoot where human demand is exceeding the biosphere's regenerative capacity (Wackernagel et al., 2002). Sterling articulates that individualised gain, corporate profit and competition need to be challenged as the drivers of climate crisis responses, because they disproportionately benefit those in the West who have generated many of these global issues. Sconfienza (2019) argues that we need to resist notions of market growth and centralisation and create space for societal and educational degrowth and decentralisation, in order to achieve a more socially just, rebalanced climate emergency response.

With its grounding in *equity*, defined as a sense of justice which can ethically resist dominant discourses, our new framework has the potential to contribute to this work (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a). Our work draws, for example, on Burnard and Colucci-Gray (2020) who argue against power hierarchies which favour individuated STEM subjects, in favour of transdisciplinarity and enactivism. Other of our characteristics can also do work here. If STEAM is practiced to forefront *inclusion, empowerment and personalisation*, it can position young learners' voices and the disenfranchised more centrally in responses to wicked problem through an emphasis on *real-world connections*. If *creativity* is forefronted as a more socially just change agent it can counter notions of creativity simply for economic gain. If *collaboration* between communities, industries and educators is prioritised it can redress a focus on maintaining the status quo of individualisation and profit. If *disciplinary inter-relations* can be understood within more flattened hierarchies between STEM and the Arts, we can begin to productively re-balance STEM-dominated agendas. We could then gain the most from transdisciplinary approaches which prioritise responding to wicked problems rather than siloed disciplines (Benatar, 2000). If *thinking-making-doing* can be prioritised over purely cognitive problem-solving, new ways of responding can emerge. We therefore endeavour next to demonstrate this in action through the case studies.

3.2. Case studies framed by the characteristics

The Road-STEAMer project is working to demonstrate the relationship between the Road-STEAMer characteristics and their manifestation within EU STEAM projects. It has therefore developed a methodology which involves drawing on the above Road STEAMer characteristics, to develop a comprehensive questionnaire for gathering detailed descriptions of EU STEAM practices.

Questionnaire development involved multiple iterations, each subjected to expert feedback from consortium STEAM researchers and professionals, which was used to ensure questions enabled the collection of meaningful data (McKenzie et al., 1999). The goal was to gather precise information on how STEAM projects manifested each of the

identified characteristics using clear and concise questions with a manageable response time. At least two questions were formulated for each characteristic, including a scaled response (ranging from 1 to 100) and a qualitative response. This approach was applied to Collaboration, Disciplinary Inter-relationships, Creativity and Inclusion/Personalization/Empowerment. For the Thinking-Making-Doing characteristic, a multiple-choice question was crafted, offering various ways to articulate these three aspects. Regarding the real-world connection characteristic, an open-ended field was offered to allow respondents to explain the connection. In designing the questionnaire, we drew pragmatically on qualitative and quantitative elements in order to conduct rigorous, practical research, with regular expert discussion at the design and interpretation phase to ensure validity (Foster, 2023).

The final version of the questionnaire consists of 35 questions, comprising three related to socio-economic context and 24 focusing on the defined characteristics, the remaining 8 used to describe project details. Efficient dissemination of the questionnaire allowed the collection of responses from 40 EU STEAM projects through purposive and snowball sampling (over time these are being added to this interactive map: <https://www.road-steamer.eu/interactive-map-of-steam-practices/>). For each of them, responses to questionnaire questions were synthesised into a concise "ID card" format, highlighting selected insights into the characteristics (see Appendix 1 ID card format). Radar diagrams were selected as an efficient visualisation method to display the manifestation of characteristics for each project (Seide et al., 2020). To construct these radar diagrams, consortium members familiarized themselves with these "ID cards," emphasising key significant aspects. Subsequently, 3 to 5 Road-STEAMer members engaged in discussions for each project to assign scores to each characteristic and create a radar diagram (see Fig.s 2 and 3). The final scores reflected either a consensus among the group or a score average if consensus was not achieved.

This overall methodology enabled a systematic and collaborative approach to assessing and visualising the diverse STEAM practices, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the characteristics whilst working robustly. The radar diagrams synthesised complex data into visual representations of characteristics, facilitating comparative analysis and insights into the effectiveness of STEAM practices, which are connected to understanding their ability to address wicked problems across Europe. This type of analysis frames the two selected case study STEAM projects which offer creative solution-seeking to the wicked problem of the climate emergency, presented next.

3.2.1. Ocean connections

'Ocean Connections' (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023b; Hetherington et al., in press; Hetherington et al., in preparation), aimed to develop students' ocean literacy through creative pedagogies (across the sciences and arts) and digital technologies. The aim was to engage primary and secondary pupils aged 7-13 (n=180) in England, Denmark and Spain intellectually and socially with the size, scale and complexity of the ocean, drawing on an ethical, activist stance to design teaching and learning that could foster pupils' sense of responsibility for and with the environment. To achieve this, the project developed a set of 'educative principles' (see https://e-learning.cesga.es/oceans_toolkit/), used by schools, aquaria and HEIs in six case study projects.

Within Road-STEAMer, Ocean Connections exemplifies an open science-open schooling approach through the relationships between aquaria, schools and HEIs in co-designing learning experiences. Aquarium educators with expertise in marine biology were available to answer questions raised by pupils, engaging in dialogue with them using an innovative collaborative virtual reality (VR) tool, alongside other digital technologies and face to face visits. Pupils were invited to respond creatively to significant real-world challenges facing the ocean, asking their own questions and engaging in problem-solving through STEAM learning using novel educational tools such as collaborative VR, augmented reality and the use of interactive educational games.

The Road-STEAMer characteristics of STEAM practice identify equity as an underpinning value of all STEAM activity, and this was the case within the Ocean Connections project. The project partners aimed to ensure an equitable approach to accessing learning, with teacher interviews highlighting their approaches to ensuring all pupils could physically access field visit sites, use of inclusive pedagogies and teacher support to scaffold use of digital technologies. Also, the idea of humans and the natural world all being equally valued within an ethical stance to the project aims was key. However, the notion of equity scored relatively low during the evaluation process described above (see Fig. 2), suggesting that whilst this principle underpinned the project design, it was not so clearly articulated in project materials: it was foundational but not foregrounded.

The project scored highly for real-world connections. Since a key part of the project was to develop pupils' connection to, as well as understanding of the Ocean, activities in projects were built around key issues facing the Ocean and humanity's role in addressing them, such as plastic pollution and fishing. Through relationships with aquaria, HEIs, and wider stakeholders such as fish markets, and harbour authorities, pupils

Fig. 2. Ocean Connections Radar diagram.

Fig. 3. Radar diagram SciCultureD.

could see how their learning was connected to the real-world and how their actions could make a difference *in* the world. The VR tool facilitated a stronger connection to the Ocean (Hetherington et al., *in press*).

Collaboration also scored highly. In Ocean Connections, pupils worked in groups within classrooms and within the collaborative VR tool, where they could interact with materials developed and placed in a VR space by other students, including internationally. Embodied and material dialogue facilitated collaboration through both real world and digital development of material-dialogic space. This collaboration was key for the students in their learning and for educators designing projects. It is also emphasised in the Ocean-human relationships, since to live ethically and responsibly in the world, humanity must be in a collaborative relationship with the ocean rather than a utilitarian one.

Creativity also scored highly in the Ocean Connections project. Creative pedagogies formed a key strand of the educative principles that underpinned the project. In practice, embodied dialogue (related to collaboration) (Chappell et al., 2019) was particularly evident, as was the role of emotion both in response to creativity-in-action and in fostering creative solutions to the core issues raised within the projects. Emotion was also linked in practice with empowerment and agency, demonstrated through the activism identified in the project evaluations, which can also be linked to the real-world connection Road-STEAMer characteristic.

Thinking-making-doing scored highly. Across all six case studies, pupils engaged in making, including creating their own digital collaborative VR spaces, exhibitions, land-art, dioramas and 'nursing grounds for fish' from chicken wire and shells which were placed in harbours and tracked using 360 cameras. These physical and digital approaches to making link to the idea of 'students as producers' with digital technologies as well as consumers of technology, connected to empowerment and agency in creative pedagogies. Through making, pupils were prompted to think deeply, reflect on and connect with the Ocean. They were also invited to take action, to 'do', through an orientation to responsible environmental activism (Chappell & Hetherington, 2023b).

Ocean Connections scored within a mid-range with respect to inclusion, personalisation and empowerment, suggesting that these characteristics were not as strongly foregrounded in the articulation of practice. It could be argued that inclusion and personalisation were both tacit elements of the practice, with educators keen to ensure that all participants could access the activities (with, for example, the digital tools used to facilitate immersive ocean experiences for those unable to

visit the ocean in person). Empowerment through creative pedagogies was a stronger aspect, linked to the aim of fostering environmental responsibility as part of ocean literacy development.

Disciplinary inter-relationships was the characteristic most weakly demonstrated in Ocean Connections. Although the project drew on a range of disciplines as part of the learning, the practices typically drew separately on these elements, blending them across the narrative of the topic but not using them in a transdisciplinary fashion (in other words, not using them as needed to address the question or problem at hand). Where disciplinary inter-relationships were evident, it was often in the use of both arts and sciences in creating experiences with the digital technologies.

The Ocean Connections project exemplifies a breadth of Road-STEAMer characteristics with some more strongly articulated. The project foregrounds real-world connections, collaboration and creativity in environmental education and demonstrates how modern educational tools such as extended reality and other digital technologies can be used in creative ways, where students-as-producers use thinking-making-doing to collaborate. and are empowered to act in response to environmental challenges. More tacitly developed are disciplinary inter-relationships and inclusion, empowerment and personalisation, and the underlying value of equity. This demonstrates the utility of the characteristics in highlighting how these aspects can be more strongly drawn upon in designing STEAM learning using creative, digital technologies.

3.2.2. SciCultureD

SciCultureD (www.scicultured.eu), building on SciCulture (Chappell et al., 2023; Wren et al., 2025), is an Erasmus-plus funded project, which designed and researched three face-to-face and blended STEAM HE intensive week-long courses (Fig. 3: Radar Diagram SciCultureD) working with 25 participants per course, a mix of undergraduate, postgraduate and staff from participating institutions. Both SciCulture and SciCultureD entwine arts, sciences, entrepreneurship and design thinking (Moreira, 2019) using creative pedagogies – dialogue; trans-disciplinarity; ethics and trusteeship; risk, immersion and play; individual, collaborative and communal activities for change (with SciCD use of the term 'individual' focused on personalisation rather than in the sense of individual gain at the expense of the collective); balance and navigation; possibilities; empowerment and agency (Chappell et al., 2016). These facilitated participants to respond to wicked problems,

connected to the climate emergency through a focus on the European Green Deal. Mixed discipline (drawn from the arts, sciences and entrepreneurship) and nationality groups (Norway, Greece, Malta and Germany) collaborated to develop innovative future visions around climate emergency responses. These were shared at the end of their weeklong course, with project partners from the arts, sciences and entrepreneurship and design thinking facilitating.

SciCultureD is spotlighted in Road-STEAMer as it provides a strong example of tertiary practice which incorporates open science. SciCultureD is freely accessible to EU HE students from undergraduate to postgraduate, and staff employed by and affiliated to HEIs through which the programme is funded. This often draws in industry professionals (e.g. from NGOs, Social Enterprises and Start-ups) who have chosen to engage in supplementary HEI-based study (often part-time, Masters-level, focused on global challenges such as sustainability). SciCultureD courses also align with Road-STEAMer foci through an emphasis on a climate emergency focused 'challenge' introduced to participants by local stakeholders situated geographically close to the face-to-face location of the course.

On equity, SciCultureD scored in the mid-range. Interestingly, this was the lowest grade of the seven; graded as such because of the competitive entry process for the courses. Despite this, equity is reflected here through its focus on experimentally resisting dominant silo-ed disciplinary HE educational approaches. It also has ethics firmly embedded within its creative pedagogies, and forefronts equal relationships between arts, sciences and entrepreneurship. SciCultureD takes a facilitatory approach to tertiary STEAM practice, with a focus on participants engaging in socially equitable responses to global climate-based challenges. The lower grading reflects the competitive nature of the project's entry process and the need for HE-level expertise.

The project scored very highly on real-world connections. SciCultureD courses centralise participant responses to real-world, wicked problems, led by community stakeholders and presented back to them at course-end where appropriate. SciCultureD then supports post-course ambassador activities to create impact from course responses. Courses are often focused on sustainability with an increasing emphasis on decolonial approaches which are directly connected to local civic and policy issues (e.g. greener, fairer, more accessible cities), requiring balance and navigation of current issues (a key SciCultureD creative pedagogy). Participants are encouraged to bring personal experiences to their inquiry-based learning and to identify with stakeholder issues personally as appropriate, and as a means to engage in follow-up ambassador projects related to the climate challenge at hand.

SciCultureD scored highly for collaboration. This is evident at all levels of SciCultureD practice through: co-teaching by facilitators to role-model transdisciplinarity; stakeholder involvement within courses; collaborative 'home group' working with up to 5 participants responding to challenges together; technologies such as Mural used to enhance this collaboration when online; creative collaborative learning styles used (e.g. creating group soundscapes, theatre and movement work, felt knowledge); and collaborative end of week group sharings. Participants are also encouraged to see collaboration as possible between disciplines and materials (e.g. plant-based and arts materials), as well as between people, and as grounded in one of the core pedagogies: individual, collaborative and communal activities for change in response to the climate emergency.

The project scored highly for thinking-making-doing demonstrated through the week. Through the combined design thinking and creative pedagogies framework many kinds of thinking, making and doing are in action in SciCultureD. Criticality is highly prized as is dialogic practice, seen as a verbal and embodied endeavour (Chappell et al., 2019), alongside problem-solving. SciCultureD activities are often very practical through both arts (e.g. movement, theatre, music and visual art activities) and sciences (e.g. small-scale experiments and engagement with peer-reviewed scientific outputs), and doing-based activities such as site-visits, maker-space engagements, alongside gamification and

online making.

SciCultureD scored relatively highly for creativity. Embodied dialogue (Chappell et al., 2019) as the core driver for creativity is one of the prioritised creative pedagogies within the courses, with an emphasis on participants developing innovative, but fit-for-purpose responses to wicked problems, whilst working with possibilities, another of the creative pedagogies. Creativity is facilitated through practical arts and sciences activities and framed via the design thinking double diamond (Drew, 2019). SciCultureD emphasises creativity as important to tertiary level STEAM-based initiatives through its creative pedagogies framework and emphasis on Open Science through climate-focused stakeholder engagement as a creative means to solve real world challenges.

The project scored relatively highly for disciplinary inter-relationship. This is reflected in its flattened hierarchy between arts, sciences and entrepreneurship, and the role-modelling of this found in co-facilitation between project partners. Participant groups are encouraged to use, move between and integrate disciplinary knowledge and practices as needed to respond to the course climate challenge. The courses are challenge/problem-based from the outset with an understanding that home groups are unlikely to 'solve' problems but find transdisciplinary ways (a core stated SciCultureD creative pedagogy) to best respond to them, and to take them out into ambassador activism post-course.

SciCultureD scored relatively low on inclusion, personalisation and empowerment. Whilst the project forefronts an inclusive, confidence-building and accessible working process for all participants through its core creative pedagogy of empowerment and agency, project evaluations (Wren et al., 2025) have demonstrated that whilst group empowerment is high, individual agency can be curtailed in service to the group. This raises questions as to how individual empowerment can be better honoured in group processes, perhaps via individuals being encouraged to work with group solutions in their own way. SciCultureD course advertising now forefronts group collaboration in order to manage expectations as to the kind of agency that will be encouraged, which is perhaps more reflective of real-world groupwork approaches to wicked problems.

Framed by the Road-STEAMer characteristics, the SciCultureD project presents a dynamic spread. Lower scores offer insight for SciCultureD regarding how personal empowerment and equity are subsumed within group agency and how this might be considered moving forward. Regarding the higher scoring elements, SciCultureD forefronts real world connections and collaboration very strongly through a project emphasis on climate-focused stakeholder involvement and, increasingly, decolonisation. The latter encapsulates much of the post-sustainability arguments for critiquing Western capitalist practices and a reduction in growth. Courses can create more socially just climate emergency responses by empowering future generations through post-course ambassador programmes which take course outcomes into real world solution seeking.

4. Discussion and conclusion

Overall, this conceptual paper explains and exemplifies a new strategic framework for STEAM education in Europe to contribute to responding to the current challenges identified as necessitating investigation by this special issue (Alvarez, Al-Noori, Doval-Ruiz, in preparation). Those challenges addressed within this paper include a lack of understanding of issues of STEAM education's cultural dynamics; and of STEAM at the intersection of secondary and tertiary levels of education; and between STEAM education and open science, especially in relation to sustainability agendas (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-70 funding scheme; Colucci-Gray et al., 2017; Goldschmidt and Bogner, 2016; Chappell & Hetherington, 2023a; Rudd, 2021).

In relation to how STEAM education can ensure balanced cultural dynamics, an issue raised by Perales and Arostegui (2021), four of the characteristics synthesised and articulated in this paper contribute here.

Equity’s definition as a ‘sense of justice’ is particularly key here as it refers to a range of STEAM education cultural dynamics including appropriate resistance to dominating disciplines, affirmative ethics, social equity and students of all kinds as learning leaders. Inclusion, Empowerment and Personalisation delves deeper into how cultural dynamics can be balanced within STEAM by focusing on acceptance of difference, especially related to identity and developing learners’ confidence, as well as raising the aspirations of under-represented groups. Collaboration builds on these nuances, bringing in technology as a tool and acknowledging student-student and teacher-teacher group work, as well as dialogue between people and all kinds of others. Disciplinary inter-relationships offers further insight in relation to cultural dynamics because this characteristic is openly defined to allow for many different kinds of relationships as culturally (in its broadest sense) appropriate, which also accommodates students’ values and brings in socio-cultural elements.

In relation to how STEAM education might more beneficially navigate the secondary-tertiary intersection and the open schooling/open science relationship, this paper offers four characteristics which are particularly pertinent. The Road-STEAMer framework’s emphasis on Real World Connections assists researchers and practitioners in understanding the relevance of including colleagues and businesses from across the STEAM professions when supporting students to shift from formal secondary education to self-selected tertiary settings. Emphasising Real World Connections and the related Thinking-Making-Doing which occurs in these settings spotlights an expectation that STEAM can have strong, hands-on impacts in the real world particularly connected to global challenges. This can help to change young people’s undergraduate choices, and career and life aspirations into previously unconsidered areas responding to issues raised around this by Holme-gaard (2015). Articulating the Disciplinary Inter-relationships as fluid and diverse rather than unidimensional is also another key contribution to knowledge of this framework as it helps to push back against disciplinary silo-ing especially in tertiary settings where HEIs are less bound by state curricula and can bring STEAM disciplines into more productive relationships as needed.

The Road-STEAMer project has analysed over 40 STEAM education practices (<https://www.road-steamer.eu/interactive-map-of-steam-practices/>) using the characteristics articulated in this paper. In the two formulated as case studies here in the context of the post sustainability agenda, there is evidence of further contributions to current gaps in both literature and practice in terms of how modern educational tools are used and how STEAM can empower the next generation (Alvarez, Al-Noori and Doval-Ruiz, in preparation). In the context of the climate emergency, the Oceans Connections project can be seen with a varied radar diagram (see Fig. 4), exemplifying the discussion above, but also showing how the use of innovative VR technology can offer immersive learning experiences in a location to which students would normally not have access. SciCultureD has a similarly varied radar diagram (see FIG.

4), again exemplifying the discussion above but also demonstrating the role of collaborative, transdisciplinary intensive practice which leads to facilitated ambassador activity geared towards activism which decolonises climate responses. The project is empowering the next generation of tertiary students to not only have confidence in their STEAM learning but to put this to use in a just way in relation to the climate emergency. Described in relation to both projects, the characteristics can also be seen starting to address the post-sustainability agenda (Sconfienza, 2019), for example in terms of how creativity is used as a socially just change agent within real world situations, and how collaboration and thinking-making-doing forefronts different ways of knowing to the solely cognitive. This reflects the fact that the theoretical frames behind both these projects align with approaches to STEAM which prioritise social, spatial and material interconnectivity (Yeomans et al., 2025). Interestingly though, the fact that both projects score lower on Equity and Inclusion, Personalisation and Empowerment demonstrates the framework’s overall utility to highlight dips such as this and to alert practitioners to what more might need to be done. In the case of Ocean Connections this is perhaps about re-energising these characteristics in technological environments, which despite their benefits, might not always promote them. In relation to SciCultureD, it is about understanding the difference between group and individual empowerment and attending to where and how it is appropriate for one or the other to dominate in a project almost entirely driven by groupwork.

Finally, the new framework itself offers a home for debates, conversations and practice developments (already being applied in over 40 European projects) in STEAM education, providing a common language but one which is open to development as new practices offer challenges. The characteristic of creativity is also emerging as a vital driver. This is particularly because, when defined in a more fluid, dialogic way (e.g. Wren et al., 2025), it can go beyond the notion of creativity as an economic imperative and work not only as a student skill, but as a means to change practice itself from within. This is highly important for STEAM which needs to change not only practice but the institutional systems within which STEAM functions. Some of these changes may yet occur through the impact of how inter- and transdisciplinary practices are implemented. In both the Ocean Connections and the SciCultureD projects scrutinised here, creativity understood diversely is core to the projects’ capacities to respond to the climate emergency in ways that acknowledge the post sustainability. Overall, we demonstrate how practitioners, professionals and researchers might work together within this framework and its characteristics to catalyse the benefits of STEAM education, particularly within an era of rapid change.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

K. Chappell: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **L. Hetherington:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Fig. 4. Radar diagrams for comparison.

Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **S. Juillard:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **C Aguirre:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **E. Duca:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix 1

This is the ID card template, it includes all possible answers to the questionnaire.

Practice ID card
Name of the practice

Socioeconomic aspects.

Inclusion policy to reach specific groups of people	Addressing social challenges	Potential barriers to join the activity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All genders - Teenagers/young adults from less privileged or disadvantaged households - Teenagers/young adults from minority cultural backgrounds - Teenagers/young adults from rural areas - Teenagers/young adults in your neighbourhood or community - Teenagers/young adults with special education needs - Teenagers/young adults with disabilities - LGBTQ+ persons - Migrants from outside the EU, refugees, asylum seekers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future employment (skills in high demand in the current job market) - Social justice (transforming unfair and violent social orders through minority’s awareness and mobilisation) - Gender’s equity improvement - Knowledge hierarchy (Increasing self-empowerment/confidence for people with low educational background) - Racism - Sexism - Mental health and wellbeing - Climate neutrality/sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accessibility of the venue (Geographic location / Mobility / Reputation) - Activity not promoted sufficiently - Cost (including participation fee, materials, etc) - Not receiving accreditation (e.g. credits or certificate) - Number of places available - Scheduled time of activity - Untrained staff / protocols for those with special educational needs and/or disabilities

Website:
Collaborating with:
School / Universities / Businesses
Other:
Format:
Open Schooling/Open Science – Scale
Description:
Need of background knowledge: Yes/No

Criteria.

Collaboration (Q.23 to 25)	Disciplinary Inter Relationships (Q.19 to 22)	Thinking-Making-Doing (Q 28 and 29)	Creativity (Q.24, 30, 31)	Real-world Connection (Q.26, 27, 28, 33)	Inclusion, Personalisation, Empowerment (Q. 15, 22, 32, 33)
<p>Collab. between participants: /100</p> <p>Tools to facilitate collab.: Technology, Game-based learning, DIY learning, Communication, Artistic practice, Creative practice, The environment</p> <p>The facilitator is</p>	<p>Are the disciplines involved of equal importance: /100</p> <p>Disciplinary inter-relationship: Multidisciplinarity, Interdisciplinarity, Transdisciplinarity</p> <p>Disciplines involved (open-ended answer)</p> <p>Roles of the arts: Developing understanding/learning in the arts/STEM,</p>	<p>Competencies used by the participants: Critical learning, Problem solving, Active behaviour, Observational skills, Object-based learning, Uncertainty management, Connection with their environment</p> <p>Balance between T/M/D: Equal emphasis to all three throughout the activity, Prioritising thinking aspect gradually integrating hands-on/practical applications,</p>	<p>Utility of participants creativity/creative thinking: /100</p> <p>Tools enabling collab: Creative practice Artistic practice</p> <p>Creativity is linked to: Innovation, Playfulness, TMD, Interdisciplinary</p>	<p>Related to a concrete problem: Yes/No</p> <p>It employs (skills): Technological skills, Entrepreneurship skills, Interdisciplinary skills, Personal development</p> <p>Participants competencies involved: Critical learning, Problem solving, Active behaviour, Observational skills, Object-based learning, Uncertainty</p>	<p>Level of accessibility: /100</p> <p>Scientific background needed: Yes/No</p> <p>Roles of the arts: Encouraging social/cultural/emotional development, Increasing self-expression, self-esteem and wellbeing,</p>

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Collaboration (Q.23 to 25)	Disciplinary Inter Relationships (Q.19 to 22)	Thinking-Making-Doing (Q 28 and 29)	Creativity (Q.24, 30, 31)	Real-world Connection (Q.26, 27, 28, 33)	Inclusion, Personalisation, Empowerment (Q. 15, 22, 32, 33)
considered as: Equal with the participants, Advisor, Guide, Top-down ed.	Contributing understanding/learning of creativity/design thinking/aesthetics, Integrating with STEM to respond to a problem, Encouraging social/cultural/emotional development, Broadening the skills and mindset of participants	Emphasising making/doing aspect minimising thinking, Allowing flexibility between the three, Separating TDM aspects in dedicated phases	connections, Collaborative support	management, Connection with their environment Participants develop their: Interest for socio-economic knowledge, Career aspiration	Broadening the skills and mindset of participants. Participants develop their: Personal development, Self-empowerment, Self-confidence, Personal meaning expression,

Responses were selected according to the response rate to the questionnaire. Only practices submitted with a 100% response rate were retained. Only fully completed questionnaires enabled us to make a relevant analysis of practices. 54 practices have been considered out of more than 100 submitted.

This is the ID card of Ocean connection practice. The answers not selected on the survey appear striped in dark grey.

Practice ID card

01 - Ocean connection

Socioeconomic aspects.

Inclusion policy to reach specific groups of people	Addressing social challenges	Potential barriers to join the activity
-All genders -Teenagers/young adults from less privileged or disadvantaged households -Teenagers/young adults from minority cultural backgrounds -Teenagers/young adults from rural areas -Teenagers/young adults in your neighbourhood or community -Teenagers/young adults with special education needs -Teenagers/young adults with disabilities -LGBTQ+ persons -Migrants from outside the EU, refugees, asylum seekers	- Social justice (transforming unfair and violent social orders through minority’s awareness and mobilisation) - Climate neutrality/sustainability -Future employment (skills in high demand in the current job market) -Gender’s equity improvement -Knowledge hierarchy (Increasing self empowerment/confidence for people with low educational background) -Racism -Sexism -Mental health and wellbeing	- Accessibility of the venue (Geographic location ≠ Mobility / Reputation) - Cost (including participation fee, materials, etc) - Number of places available -Activity not promoted sufficiently -Not receiving accreditation (e.g. credits or certificate) -Scheduled time of activity -Untrained staff / protocols for those with special educational needs and/or disabilities

Website:

<https://www.ocean-connections.net/en/enhome-pageesiniocioglinicio-english/>

Collaborating with:

School / Universities / Businesses

Format: Educational Projects with schools/aquaria/HEIs

Open Schooling – European level

Description:

The Ocean Connections project was an EU funded (Erasmus+) project to promote the teaching of ocean literacy using creative and digital pedagogies. It used STEAM approaches to connect aquaria as informal learning centres with formal schooling, informed by research evidence. 6 projects were run within schools, teaching about different facets of ocean literacy and underpinned by educative principles developed from the project using a research base that connected STEAM creative pedagogies, science in society research, ocean literacy principles and research into effective use of digital technologies. The project took place in the UK, Spain and Denmark.

Need of background knowledge: **No**

Criteria.

Collaboration	Disciplinary Inter Relationships	Thinking-Making-Doing	Creativity	Real-world Connection	Inclusion, Personalisation, Empowerment
Collab. between participants: 76/100 Tools to facilitate collab.: Technology, Game-based learning,	Are the disciplines involved of equal importance: 74/100. Disciplinary inter-relationship: Transdisciplinarity, Multidisciplinarity, Interdisciplinarity	Competencies used by the participants: Critical learning, Problem solving, Active behaviour, Connection with their environment Observational skills, Object based learning, Uncertainty management Balance between T/M/D:	Utility of participants creativity/creative thinking: 75/100 Tools enabling collab: Creative practice Artistic practice	Related to a concrete problem: Yes (Each project activity focused on a particular aspect of ocean literacy and related to a key issue (e.g. plastic pollution, fish stocks)	Level of accessibility: 59/100. Scientific background needed: No Roles of the arts: Increasing self-

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Collaboration	Disciplinary Inter Relationships	Thinking-Making-Doing	Creativity	Real-world Connection	Inclusion, Personalisation, Empowerment
Communication, Creative practice, the environment. DIY learning, Artistic practice, The facilitator is considered as: Guide Equal with the participants, Advisor, Top-down ed.	Disciplines involved: Science, Geography, Arts, Digital technology Roles of the arts: Contributing understanding/ learning of creativity/design thinking, Integrating with STEM to respond to a problem Contributing understanding/ learning of aesthetics, Developing understanding/ learning in the arts/STEM, Encouraging social/cultural/emotional development, Broadening the skills and mindset of participants.	Equal emphasis to all three throughout the activity Prioritising thinking aspect gradually integrating hands-on/practical applications, Emphasising making/ doing aspect minimising thinking, Allowing flexibility between the three, Separating TDM aspects in dedicated phases.	Creativity is linked to: TMD, Interdisciplinary connections Innovation, Playfulness, Collaborative support.	It employs (skills): Technological skills, Interdisciplinary skills, Personal development Entrepreneurship skills Participants competencies involved: Critical learning, Problem solving, Active behaviour, Connection with their environment Observational skills, Object-based learning, Uncertainty management Participants develop their: Interest for socio-economic knowledge Career aspiration	expression, self-esteem and wellbeing Encouraging social/cultural/emotional development, Broadening the skills and mindset of participants. Participants develop their: Personal development, Self-empowerment, Self-confidence, Personal meaning expression

References

- ACE (Arts Council England) (n.d.) STEAM toolkit powering your STEM curriculum through arts, culture and creativity. Arts Council England.
- Allina, B. (2017). The development of STEAM educational policy to promote student creativity and social empowerment. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 119(2), 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632913.2017.1296392>
- Bautista, A. (2021). STEAM education: Contributing evidence of validity and effectiveness. *Journal for the Study of Education and Development*, 44(4), 755–768. <https://doi.org/10.1080/021103702.2021.1926678>
- Benatar, S. (2000). Perspectives from physicians and medical scientists. In M. A. Somerville, & D. J. Rapport (Eds.), *Transdisciplinarity: recreating integrated knowledge* (pp. 171–192). McGill-Queen's University Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt7zw15.12>
- Burnard, J., & Colucci-Gray, L. (Eds.). (2020). *Why science and art creativities matter: (Re) configuring STEAM for future-making education*. Brill Sense. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004421585>
- Burns, K., Cahill-Jones, T., Carter, C., Stint, C., & Veart, L. (Eds.). (2021). *STEAM Approaches Handbook*. Birmingham City University: STEAM INC.
- Carter, C. E., Barnett, H., Burns, K., Cohen, N., Durall, E., Lordick, D., Nack, F., Newman, A., & Usher, S. (2021). Defining STEAM approaches for higher education. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 6(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.20897/ejsteme/11354>
- Center for STEAM Education Research. (2018). Science communication and innovation. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/763594>. Retrieved 20 November 2022.
- Chappell, K., & Hetherington, L. (2023). Creative pedagogies in digital STEAM practices: natural, technological and cultural entanglements for powerful learning and activism. *Cultural Studies of Science Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-023-10200-4>
- Chappell, K. and Hetherington, L. (2023a). Road STEAMer, Deliverable 4.1 Research Framework (criteria).
- Chappell, K., Hetherington, L., Alexopoulos, A., Ben-Horin, O., Nikolopoulos, K., Ruck-Keene, H., ... Sotiriou, S. (2019). Dialogue and materiality/embodiment in science/ arts creative pedagogy: Their role and manifestation. *Thinking Skills and Creativity Special Issue. Exploring Pedagogies of Dialogic Space*, 31, 296–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2018.12.008>
- Chappell, K., Witt, S., Wren, H., Hampton, L., Swinford, L., Woods, P., & Hampton, M. (2023). Re-creating higher education pedagogy by making materiality and spatiality matter. *Special Issue of Journal of Creative Behaviour: Beyond Western Notions of Creativity in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jobc.619>
- Chappell, K., Hetherington, L., Ruck-Keene, H., Slade, C., & Cukurova, M. (2016). CREATIONS D2.1 the features of inquiry learning: Theory, research and practice. Retrieved 4 July 2019 <https://www.creations-project.eu>
- Choi, S., Won, A., Chu, H., Cha, H., Shin, H., & Kim, C. (2021). The impacts of a climate change SSI-STEAM program on junior high school students' climate literacy. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 7(1), 96–133. <https://doi.org/10.1163/23641177-bja10019>
- Chung, S. K., & Li, D. (2021). Issues-based STEAM education: A case study in a Hong Kong secondary school. *International Journal of Education & the Arts*, 22(3). <http://doi.org/10.26209/ijea22n3>
- Colucci-Gray, L., Burnard, P., Cooke, C., Davies, R., Gray, D., & Trowsdale, J. (2017). *Reviewing the potential and challenges of developing STEAM education through creative pedagogies for 21st learning: how can school curricula be broadened towards a more responsive, dynamic, and inclusive form of education?* British Educational Research Association. <https://www.bera.ac.uk/project/reviewing-the-potential-and-challenges-of-developing-steam-education>
- Costantino, T. (2017). STEAM by another name: Transdisciplinary practice in art and design education. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 119(2), 100–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632913.2017.1292973>
- CREAM Project. (n.d.). creamproject.eu – Cream. Retrieved October 10, 2022, from <https://creamproject.eu/>
- Dredd, D., Kellam, N., & Jayasuriya, S. (2021). Zen and the art of STEAM: Student knowledge and experiences in interdisciplinary and traditional engineering academic experiences. In *2021 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)* (pp. 1–9). IEEE.
- Drew, C. (2019). The Double Diamond: 15 years on. Design Council <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/news-opinion/double-diamond-15-years>
- eCraft2Learn. (2019). eCraft2Learn: Digital Fabrication and maker Movement in Education: Making computer-supported artefacts from scratch. CORDIS | European Commission <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/300711-fun-inventive-and-dynamic-new-approaches-to-digital-skills-and-making-technologies>
- European Economic and Social Committee. (2020). Towards an EU strategy for enhancing green skills and competencies for all. <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/towards-eu-strategy-enhancing-green-skills-and-competences-all-own-initiative-opinion>
- Foster, C. (2023). Methodological pragmatism in educational research: From qualitative-quantitative to exploratory-confirmatory distinctions. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 47(1), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743727X.2023.2210063>
- Foundations of STEAM. (n.d.). Arts integration. Retrieved November 20, 2022, from <https://artsintegration.com/2016/04/01/foundations-of-steam/>
- Fram, S. (2013). The constant comparative analysis method outside of grounded theory. *The Qualitative Report*, 18(1), 1–25. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1004995.pdf>
- Goldschmidt, M., & Bogner, F. (2016). Learning about genetic engineering in an outreach laboratory: Influence of motivation and gender on students' cognitive achievement. *International Journal of Science Education*, 6(2), 166–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21548455.2015.1031293>. Part B.
- Graham, M. (2021). The disciplinary borderlands of education: Art and STEAM education. *Infancia y Aprendizaje. Journal for the Study of Education and Development*, 44(4), 769–800.
- Guyotte, K. W. (2020). Toward a philosophy of STEAM in the anthropocene. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 52(7), 769–779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2019.1690989>
- Harris, A., & de Bruin, L. (2018). Secondary school creativity, teacher practice and STEAM education: An international study. *Journal of Educational Change*, 19, 153–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-017-9311-2>
- Hetherington, L., Brandt, H., Chappell, K., Dillon, J., & Malmierca, M. J. R.. (in press). Understanding the material-dialogic nature of digital spaces in ocean literacy education. *Environmental Education Research*.
- Hetherington, L., Brandt, H., Nielsen, B. L., Dillon, J., & Yeomans, L. (in preparation). Guiding principles for ocean literacy education: Using digital tools with creative, material-dialogic pedagogies. *Research in Science Education*.
- Holbrook, J., Rannikmäe, M., & Soobard, R. (2020). STEAM education—A transdisciplinary teaching and learning approach. In B. Akpan, & T. J. Kennedy (Eds.), *Science Education in Theory and Practice* (pp. 465–477). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-9_31
- Holmegaard, H. T. (2015). Performing a choice-narrative: A qualitative study of the patterns in STEM students' higher education choices. *International Journal of Science Education*, 37(9), 1454–1477. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2015.1042940>
- Huser, J., et al. (2020). *STEAM and the Role of the Arts in STEM*. State Education Agency Directors of Arts Education.
- Hye-Eun, C. (2021). Editorial: STEAM education in the Asia Pacific Region. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 7(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1163/23641177-bja10026>

- IMuSciCA (Interactive Music Science Collaborative Activities). (2019). CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731861>. Retrieved November 20, 2022.
- Jesionkowska, J., Wild, F., & Deval, Y. (2020). Active learning augmented reality for STEAM education - A case study. *Education Sciences*, 10(8), 198. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10080198>
- Johnson-Green, E., Lee, C., & Flannery, M. (2020). A musical perspective on STEM: Evaluating the EcoSonic Playground Project from a Co-equal STEAM integration standpoint. *International Journal of Education & the Arts*, 21(14).
- Katz-Buonincontro, J. (2018). Gathering STE(A)M: Policy, curricular, and programmatic developments in arts-based science, technology, engineering, and mathematics education. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 119(2), 73–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632913.2017.1407979>
- Kemp, L., Xu, C., Depledge, J., Ebi, K., Gibbins, G., Kohler, T., Rockström, J., Scheffer, M., Schellnhuber, H., Steffen, W., & Lenton, T. (2022). Climate endgame: Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(e2108146119). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2108146119>
- Kolko, J. (2012). *Wicked problems: problems worth solving: A handbook and a call to action*. Texas: Austin Center for Design.
- Koul, A., Ganju, S., Kasam, M. & Parr, J. (2021). SpaceML: Distributed open-source research with citizen scientists for the advancement of Space technology for NASA. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2012.10610>.
- Liao, C. (2016). From Interdisciplinary to transdisciplinary: An arts-integrated approach to STEAM education. *Art Education*, 69(6), 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00043125.2016.1224873>
- Liston, M., Morrin, A. M., Furlong, T., & Griffin, L. (2022). Integrating data science and the Internet of Things into science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics education through the use of new and emerging technologies. *Frontiers in Education*, 348(7). <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.757866>
- Liu, C., & Wu, C. (2022). STEM without art: A ship without a sail. *Thinking Skills & Creativity*, 43, Article 100977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2021.100977>
- Martinez, J. (2017). *The search for method in STEAM education*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55822-6>
- Massaro, M., Dumay, J., & Guthrie, J. (2016). On the shoulders of giants? Undertaking a structured literature review in accounting. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 29(5), 767–801. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-01-2015-1939>
- McKenzie, J. F., Wood, M. L., Kotecki, J. E., Clark, J. K., & Brey, R. A. (1999). Establishing content validity: Using qualitative and quantitative steps. *American Journal of Health Behaviour*, 23(4), 311–318.
- Moreira, M. (2019). Making design education (even more) complex: Exploring complexity for an amplified mindset of design. *International Journal of Art and Design Education*, 38(4), 769–784. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jade.12266>
- Ng, W., & Fergusson, J. (2020). Engaging high school girls in interdisciplinary STEAM. *Science Education International*, 31(3), 283–294. <https://doi.org/10.33828/sei.v31.i3.7>
- OSHub Open Science Hub Network. (2022). OSHub Open Science Hub Network: Empowering citizens through STEAM education with open schooling. CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824581/reporting>. Retrieved November 12, 2022.
- Paez, A. (2017). Grey literature: An important resource in systematic reviews. *Journal of Evidence Based Medicine*, 10(3), 233–240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jebm.12266>
- Perales, F. J., & Aróstegui, J. L. (2021). The STEAM approach: Implementation and educational, social and economic consequences. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 0(0), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632913.2021.1974997>
- Perignat, E., & Katz-Buonincontro, J. (2019). STEAM in practice and research: An integrative literature review. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 31, 31–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2018.10.002>
- PHERECLOS (Partnerships for pathways to Higher Education and science engagement in Regional Clusters of Open Schooling). (2020). CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824630/reporting>. Retrieved November 12, 2022.
- Quigley, C., & Herro, D. (2019). *An Educator's Guide to STEAM: Engaging Students Using Real-World Problems*. Teachers College Press. <https://doi.org/10.22550/2174-0909.3177>
- Research is Your Elevation. (2024). CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101162548> (Accessed June 10, 2024).
- Ripple, W., Wolf, C., Gregg, J., Levin, K., Rockstrom, J., Newsome, T., Betts, M., Huq, S., Law, B., Kemp, L., Kalmus, P., & Lenton, T. (2022). *World Scientists' Warning of a Climate Emergency 2022*. Oxford University Press/American Institute of Biological Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biac083>
- Rocco, T. S., Plakhotnik, M. S., McGill, C. M., Huyler, D., & Collins, J. C. (2023). Conducting and writing a structured literature review in Human Resource development. *Human Resource Development Review*, 22(1), 104–125. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15344843221141515>
- Rudd, J. (2021). We're all in this together' - solving climate change across the disciplines by taking a STEAM approach to climate education. *School Science Review*, 102(383), 42–47.
- Salehjee, S., & Watts, M. (2023). STEAM success stories": Refocusing the framework of intersectionality. *London Review of Education*, 21(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.21.1.32>
- Sarmiento, C., Morales, M., Elipane, L., & Palomar, B. (2020). Assessment practices in Philippine higher STEAM education. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 17(5), 1–15.
- SciCulture (n.d.) <https://sciculture.eu/> Retrieved November 18, 2022.
- Sconfienza, U. (2019). The post-sustainability trilemma. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 21(6), 769–784. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2019.1673156>
- Scuolattiva (n.d.). STEAM 4 Future. <https://www.scuolattiva.it/project/steam-4-future/> Retrieved November 18, 2022.
- Seide, S., Jensen, K., & Kieser, M. (2020). Utilizing radar graphs in visualization of simulation and estimation results in network meta-analysis. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 12(1), 96–105. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1412>
- Shatunova, O., Anisimova, T., Sabirova, F., & Kalimullina, O. (2019). STEAM as an innovative educational technology. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 10(2), 131–144.
- Sochaka, N., Guyott, K., & Walther, J. (2016). Learning together: A collaborative autoethnographic exploration of STEAM education. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 105(1), 15–42.
- Sterling, S. (2017). Assuming the future: Repurposing education in a volatile age. In S. Sterling, & B. Jickling (Eds.), *Post-Sustainability and Environmental Education: Remaking Education for the Future* (pp. 31–45). Pivot Press/Palgrave. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51322-5>.
- Suganda, S., Latifah, S., Irwandani, Sari, P. M., Rahmayanti, H., Ichsan, I. Z., & Rahman, M. M. (2021). STEAM and environment on students' creative-thinking skills: A meta-analysis study. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1796, Article 012101. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1796/1/012101>
- Thomassen, A., & Stentoft, D. (2020). Educating students for a complex future - Why integrating a problem analysis in problem-based learning has something to offer. *The Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.14434/ijpbl.v14i2.28804>
- Wackernagel, M., Schulz, N., Deumling, D., Linares, A., Jenkins, M., Kapos, V., Monfreda, C., Loh, J., Myers, N., Norgaard, R., et al. (2002). Tracking the ecological overshoot of the human economy. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 99, 9266–9271. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.142033699>
- Won, A., Choi, S., Chu, H., Cha, H., Shin, H., & Kim, C. (2021). A teacher's practical knowledge in an SSI-STEAM program dealing with climate change. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 7(1), 134–172. <https://doi.org/10.1163/23641177-bja10023>
- Wren, H., Hetherington, L., Chappell, K., Duca, E., O'Kane, E., Quacinella, D., ... Sotiriou, M. (2025). Conceptualising and exploring creative pedagogies and design thinking in transdisciplinary STEAM higher education courses. 10.1080/02671522.2025.2493622.
- Yeomans, L., Chappell, K., Hetherington, L., Bresciani, S., Unterfrauner, E., Fabian, C., & Koulouris, P. (2025). STEAM Education: A Four-fold Conceptual Framework. *International Journal of STEM Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15020164>.
- Zhbanova, K. S. (2017). How the arts standards support STEM concepts: A journey from STEM to STEAM. *Journal of STEM Arts, Crafts, and Constructions*, 2(2), 1.